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Credibility of Social Media Influencers and the Impulse Buying Behavior of Generation Z Customers

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the most purchased items which are apparel, shoes, and accessories, using the social media platform in which the social media influencers advertises such products through their online content. The purpose of this study is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the credibility of social media influencers on the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z customers in Angeles City, Pampanga. The researcher conducted an online survey among 403 respondents who are college students and young professionals, within the age bracket of 18-30 years old. The study employed descriptive correlational research design. The findings revealed that Generation Z customers generally agreed that the influencers they watch and follow are credible. Among the credibility factors, trustworthiness gained the highest influence on impulse buying behavior. While Generation Z exhibits impulsive tendencies, the results show that they are more likely to engage in an impulsive buying behavior when they perceive such product as useful or necessary, especially when it is advertised or reviewed by the social media influencers they follow. The study recommended that brands may consider partnering with trustworthy social media influencers who displays expertise, charisma, and attractive lifestyle. Emphasizing the 'need' to purchase the product, together with good promotional strategies may highly lead to impulse buying behavior among Generation Z customers. In exploring the correlation between the credibility of social media influencers on the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z, the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the variables.

Keywords: Credibility of Social Media Influencers, Impulse Buying Behavior, Generation Z, Young Professional, Apparel

INTRODUCTION

Technology has brought tremendous changes to our daily lives, and its effect is manifested across all ages. One advent of technology is the use of social media, which started as a platform aiming to connect people, enabling them to make friends all around the globe. Davis (2015) defines social media as an online platform that enables users to create, organize, and share content either individually or collaboratively. As of February 2025, out of 5.56 billion individuals, 67.9 % of the global population are internet users. Among them, 5.24 billion, or 63.9 percent of the world's population, are social media users (Petrosyan, 2025).

Initially, communicating with friends and family was the main purpose of social media. However, as websites like Facebook and Twitter achieved mainstream acceptance, their usage rapidly increased. Due to their ability to rapidly connect with a global audience, these platforms were especially appealing to businesses. One of the most engaging kind of media is social networks, with a recorded daily usage of 2.24 hours in 2020 around the globe. According to Global Web Index, 46% of internet users globally access news through social media platforms, surpassing the 40% of users who

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see news on websites. Generation Z and millennials were more inclined to consume news on social media compared to other generations (Investopedia, 2021).

The use of social media, especially TikTok, grew significantly during the pandemic since people were stuck in their homes (Raza et al., 2023). Based on observations, people who uploaded videos did not anticipate that their videos or content would capture the interest of viewers, or in some cases, become trending. Other uploaders, who initially thought of sharing their daily lives through uploaded videos, did not imagine that brands would come knocking on their doors for brand partnerships, making them instant influencers.

According to Schaffer (2022), one way to earn money on TikTok is by becoming a content creator or social media influencer. This will be achieved by gaining a lot of followers on various online platforms. Since the content of materials uploaded is one of the reasons to gain followers, it is important to assess how content creators or influencers are perceived in terms of credibility and trustworthiness.

In Bangkok, Thailand, the study of Pattavet (2023) proved that consumers purchase fashion products to gain acceptance. Additionally, identifying themselves as similar to some revered social media influencers in terms of lifestyle and preferences creates a positive attitude towards purchasing a product endorsed by that influencer.

Social Media Influencers in the Philippines have become a major driving tool in advertising certain brands or services. These influencers use different social media platforms to create content, particularly videos, in their accounts. Some of them started as vloggers utilizing YouTube platforms, such as "Cong TV" with 3.2M followers on TikTok and 12.1M subscribers on YouTube. Due to the availability and ease of use of Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok, vloggers utilize these platforms to advertise and partner with different brands. The goal is to personally try and experience a particular brand, then create content, using an honest review of the product or service.

Consumers have different preferences, sets of beliefs, perspectives, and behaviors. Because of this, a marketing agent's engagement with social media influencers may help with the social media presence of a particular brand. Social media influencers offer credibility and leverage in terms of their expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness, which may help them in the branding of such products.

Cobb (2024) explains expertise as "having an extensive knowledge and proficiency in a particular field or discipline". It is typically acquired through years of experience. One of its domains – Credibility- is one of the strengths of experts, which they have accumulated through their experience, education, portfolios, credentials, achievements, and other accomplishments, which leads to showcasing their expertise.

On the other hand, the term attractiveness pertains to a person's qualities, characteristics, or traits that generate positive emotions, interest, and desire for social interaction. This encompasses various elements such as personality, intelligence, social abilities, physical appearance, and other traits (Agthe et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, Hudders et al. (2020) indicated that trustworthiness is an essential element of the source expertise. Social media influencers must have this trait to ensure that they are perceived as trustworthy by their followers and effectively endorse products and services (Schouten et al., 2020).

That said, marketers should focus on promoting their brand image by selecting the best-fitted social media influencer to produce relevant content for their target customers to increase product sales (Qadeer & Aleem, 2024). The study of Soengas-Pérez et al. (2023) concluded that credibility has been understood as a complex concept shaped by a process of how various filters influence people's perception of facts. In this way, a single story may be interpreted in many ways, depending on the subjective perspective of different individuals.

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This study chose to focus on apparel, shoes, and accessories, which are observed to be the most viewed and purchased products by Generation Z. According to Chen & Dalangin (2021), apparel is one of the businesses that has increased significantly in the online business industry. Reviews from social media influencers can lead to different types of impulse buying behavior, such as pure, reminder, suggested, and planned, once watched or viewed by Generation Z.

Impulse buying behavior is defined as a spontaneous feeling or emotion that transpires when a person is exposed to a variety of information about a product or service, often leading to immediate purchase. Buil et al. (2019) found that social media platforms play a crucial role in triggering impulse buying behavior, as they offer a constant stream of product recommendations and promotions that can influence consumers' decision-making process.

Mathur (2019) defined pure impulse buying as an escape purchase, where a shopper deviates from their usual shopping habits. Reminder Impulse buying happens when the shopper recalls the need for a product while in the shopping process. Suggestion impulse buying occurs when a shopper decides to purchase a new product based on self-persuasion, without any prior plan or intention of buying it. Lastly, planned impulse buying happens when a purchase is somewhat pre-planned, but the buyer has no decision yet on what exact product or category to buy.

Consumers are mostly caught off guard every time a special deal comes with a product or service, prompting them to purchase. This occurrence unknowingly falls under one or more of the four different types of impulse buying behavior. This instance may occur with the presence of social media influencers through their content on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok. Tolentino et al. (2023) discovered that the young professionals' impulse buying selections in Angeles City, Pampanga, had a substantial association with online selling via social media.

One of the most prominent users of technology is the so-called "Generation Z." The COVID-19 pandemic has strengthened the use of technologies and gadgets, especially in communicating through social media platforms. It also opened new opportunities for content creators in becoming "Social Media Influencers", offering more opportunities of collaboration with different companies that want more exposure for their products. The goal of collaboration between the company and the social media influencers is to stimulate the purchasing behavior and decision-making process of those who idolize the content creator.

According to McKinsey & Company (2019), Generation Z is the generation born roughly between 1995 to 2010. They are considered true digital natives as they are already exposed to the internet, social networks, and mobile technology even at an early age. As a result, they have evolved into a hypercognitive generation, skilled at gathering and cross-referencing information from multiple sources and seamlessly integrating virtual and real-life experiences.

The Generation Z cohort has adopted online shopping as a popular trend (Hinduan et al., 2020). In fact, it has become a routine for many young people to shop online to the extent that, in Brown's study (2017), despite most customers preferring to touch and feel the products in-store before purchasing, 67% of people use their phones to make online orders while at the store. For companies that operate online platforms, Generation Z customers are crucial as they not only utilize their products and services but also offer innovative solutions and feedback that help businesses enhance their product offerings. Thus, Generation Z's role in influencing the improvement of products and services has become more significant.

The purpose of this research was to provide insight into the role that the credibility of social media influencers plays in shaping impulse buying behavior among Generation Z in Angeles City, Pampanga. Research conducted in the past solely focused on either the credibility of social media influencers or impulse buying behavior. Additionally, studies were more on consumer buying behavior and not much on impulse buying behavior. Furthermore, there is limited data on the connection or

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relationship between the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior (pure, reminder, suggested, planned) in the Philippines. The study was essential and useful for apparel, shoes, and accessories businesses, social media marketers, and social media influencers looking to target this demographic, as it provided valuable insight into the factors that influence Generation Z's impulse buying behavior.

Conceptual Framework

This study aimed to describe whether there is a significant relationship between social media influencers and the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z consumers in Angeles City, Pampanga. The theoretical underpinning for this study was based on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), which emphasizes the role of observational learning, modeling, and reinforcement in the acquisition and maintenance of behavior.

The Social Cognitive Theory postulates that people are active participants in their environment and are not only shaped by it. This further suggests that individuals can acquire knowledge through observing others in social settings, through personal experiences, and through exposure to media. Bandura (1986) assumes that human behavior is often influenced by personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. When an individual is exposed to someone performing a behavior and sees the outcomes of the action, they tend to retain that sequence and use it to shape their future behaviors. Furthermore, watching a model can trigger individuals to act on what they previously learned.

In the context of this study, social media influencers are considered models that may influence the impulse buying behavior (reinforcement) of Generation Z through their video content on various social media platforms (observational learning). The credibility of social media influencers consists of three factors, namely: Expertise, Attractiveness, and Trustworthiness. These credibility factors were explored to identify their effect on the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z customers, leading to immediate purchase. Impulse buying, on the other hand, consists of four factors namely: Pure, Reminder, Suggested, and Planned impulse buying behavior.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

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Research Objectives

The study aimed at addressing the following research questions:

1. How does the credibility of social media influencers describe in terms of:
 - 1.1 expertise,
 - 1.2 attractiveness, and
 - 1.3 trustworthiness?
2. How may Generation Z's impulse buying behavior be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Pure impulse buying behavior,
 - 2.2 Reminder impulse buying behavior,
 - 2.3 Suggested impulse buying behavior, and
 - 2.4 Planned impulse buying behavior?
3. How does the credibility of social media influencers relate to the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z?

Hypothesis

H₁: The credibility of social media influencers is related to the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive correlational research design to describe the credibility of social media influencers, which leads to impulse buying behavior of Generation Z. The data were gathered through a survey questionnaire, and the results were interpreted to draw a conclusion.

The study was considered descriptive since it described the credibility of social media influencers in terms of their expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness. Furthermore, the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z in terms of pure, reminder, suggested, and planned impulse buying behavior was also identified. The study was correlational, for it identified the significant relationship between the credibility of social media influencers on the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z.

Sampling Design

The researcher used a random sampling design commonly used in quantitative research employing survey questionnaires. This is particularly useful in uniform populations, where everyone has an equal chance of being randomly chosen. Random sampling is a popular method due to its ease, speed, and affordability.

In this study, the researcher aimed to analyze the relationship between social media influencers and impulse buying behavior of Generation Z. She also ensured that the survey questionnaires were distributed randomly, providing an equal opportunity to all the qualified respondents to participate. Additionally, the researcher utilized this sampling design, ensuring the willingness of the respondents to participate in the study.

Participants of the Study

The research included 403 individuals from Angeles City, Pampanga. The researcher used Raosoft Software, available on the online platform Raosoft.com, to determine the total sample size required. This tool facilitated calculation based on parameters to ensure the sample was significant. The parameters chosen for this calculation included a 5% margin of error, which represented the

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allowable amount of error, and a 95% confidence level, reflecting the acceptable level of uncertainty. The confidence level of 95% was a common selection in research. This percentage indicated the level of confidence that the true population parameter lay within the calculated margin of error.

The calculated sample size aimed to provide a subset of the population to provide insights into the relationship between the credibility of social media influencers to the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z.

The respondents were composed of young professionals and college students residing in Angeles City, Pampanga. The study focused on the impulsive tendencies of Generation Z consumers when exposed to social media influencers' reviews as content, especially for products such as apparel, shoes, and accessories. Inclusion criteria for participants were the following: Young professionals who were 21-30 years of age at the time of the study (still within the Generation Z age bracket) and College students within the age range of 18-30 years old.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher selected a survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument to provide specific, unbiased, and direct responses. Additionally, it was cost-effective since respondents could answer on digital questionnaires. An appropriate survey questionnaire was adapted, which was suitable for the researcher's field of study.

The researcher primarily utilized the distribution of the survey questionnaire to the target respondents who are Generation Z, with the age range of 18-30 years old, in Angeles City, Pampanga. The survey questionnaire aimed to collect data on the relationship between the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior among the respondents.

Google Form was utilized for ease of access and a timely report of the results. The survey questionnaire was designed to gather information on various aspects of social media influencers, including their expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness, as well as various aspects of impulse buying behavior, including pure, reminder, suggested, and planned impulse buying. The data collected through the survey was analyzed using statistical techniques to determine the relationship between social media influencers and impulse buying behavior among Generation Z in Angeles City, Pampanga.

Research Instrument

The study focused on two major variables: Credibility of Social Media Influencers and Impulse Buying Behavior.

To measure the credibility of social media influencers, the researcher adapted the questionnaire from Baig and Shahzad's (2022) study. The questionnaire was comprised of two (2) initial questions with two options each, followed by twelve (12) declarative statements grouped into three (3) sub-variables: Expertise, Attractiveness, and Trustworthiness, with four (4) declarative statements for each sub-variable. The questionnaire yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.825 for expertise, 0.845 for attractiveness, and 0.842 for trustworthiness. All subscales demonstrated good reliability, as Cronbach's alpha values that are greater than 0.6 are generally considered satisfactory.

To measure impulse buying behavior, the researcher used a questionnaire adapted from Barcelona et al.'s (2022) study. The questionnaire comprised one (1) initial question followed by twenty-four (24) declarative statements grouped into four (4) sub-variables: Pure, Reminder, Suggested, and Planned, with six (6) declarative statements for each sub-variable. The researcher used a Likert Scale to measure the credibility of social media influencers and the impulse buying behavior of the respondents. In answering the questions, the respondents have five (5) options: Strongly Agree, Agree,

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Neither Agree nor Disagree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree, and one of each option has a corresponding point that will be used in the computation of the statistical treatment. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents. Internal consistency of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, with reliability coefficients for the dimensions of impulsive buying falling within the range of 0.74 to 0.85.

Data Analysis

The researcher used several statistical methods to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the gathered data regarding the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior among Generation Z. The calculations of mean, Likert Scale, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized.

Mean was calculated to assess the data related to the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior. This involved determining the mathematical average by summation of all the data set values, then dividing that total by the number of items.

This study also utilized a Likert Scale to record respondents' answers in the online questionnaire with a rating system in describing the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior of Generation Z. All respondents provided their perspectives, enhancing the depth of understanding and analysis in the next chapters of this research. This approach captures both the cognitive and emotional aspects of the respondents.

In assessing the Likert Scale on the credibility of social media influencers and impulse buying behavior, the researcher categorized the responses as follows:

Table 1
5-Point Likert Scale

Scale	Range	Description
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Neither Agree nor Disagree
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree

Pearson correlation coefficient was used to evaluate the correlation between the variables. This is the most used method for measuring a linear correlation which quantifies the magnitude and direction of the association between two variables on a scale ranging from -1 to 1.

Multiple Linear Regression was used to find the relationship between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables. This had been utilized to examine how the credibility of social media influencers affects impulse buying behavior among Generation Z.

All the data and interpretations were presented using tables to ensure clarity and accessibility in presenting the research findings.

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Ethical Considerations

In conducting research projects, ethical considerations are of utmost importance because respondents have moral and legal rights that need to be protected. To ensure that individuals were protected in this study, the researcher used Informed Consent to guarantee that privacy was not violated, feelings were not harmed, and any information received from them was accurately represented. The survey questionnaire did not impose any obligation on respondents to participate in or review the questionnaires. Instead, the study was conducted through voluntary participation, via Google Form. The study also ensured that respondents' decisions were valued and respected.

The study took several ethical considerations into account, such as privacy and confidentiality, safety, autonomy, dignity, and informed consent. Privacy and confidentiality were maintained by ensuring that the information provided was unidentifiable by anyone other than the researcher. Safety was ensured by eliminating any consistent risk elements and certifying the accuracy of any information to be gathered. Autonomy was respected by ensuring that respondents' contributions were voluntary and that they could withdraw from the research at any time. Dignity was preserved by allowing respondents to make fully informed decisions and treating them with respect. Informed consent was obtained by providing participants with a letter and consent form that explained the key elements of the study, the role of the researcher, and their role as respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Credibility of Social Media Influencers

The participant's responses to the credibility of social media influencers questionnaire played an important role leading towards identifying its effect on impulse buying behavior among Generation Z customers. This study described the credibility of social media influencers in terms of expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness.

1.1. Expertise

Table 2 presented the Generation Z's perception regarding social media influencers in terms of expertise. Expertise refers to the extent to which social media influencers are perceived to be experts, knowledgeable, have a wide perspective, and are credible.

Table 2
Credibility of Social Media Influencers: Expertise

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are experts in their field.	4.00	0.751	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow have great knowledge about their field.	4.09	0.698	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow explain products through every perspective.	4.02	0.787	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow provide references based on their expertise.	4.07	0.782	Agree
Composite Mean	4.05		Agree

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The results showed that Generation Z follows social media influencers who are experts in their field, which is evident with the composite mean of 4.05, having all questions answered with "Agree". The standard deviation ranged from 0.698 to 0.787. It indicated a low variability in Generation Z's responses, which meant that they shared similar perceptions about social media influencers' expertise. The result of this study was contrary to the findings of Wiedmann & von Mettenheim (2021), which showed that trustworthiness is the most important requirement in an online influencer campaign on an entry-level luxury fashion brand. Trustworthiness was followed by attractiveness, and expertise was found to be of no influence at all.

The second statement showed the highest mean score of 4.09, having a standard deviation of 0.698. This indicated a strong agreement that social media influencers are perceived as knowledgeable in promoting products, mainly apparel, shoes, and accessories. On the contrary, the first statement indicated the lowest mean of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.751. This suggested an overall agreement with the statement. These findings suggested that the respondents perceive that the social media influencers they follow are credible sources of information.

Meanwhile, the third statement has a mean of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.787. The respondents agreed that the social media influencer they follow explains the products from every perspective. Generation Z is known to have a short attention span, which may affect their choice to continue watching video content. If they perceived that the video had a long duration, they might not finish such content. Social media influencers may have already considered the said factor, making their content straightforward and short, to retain the attention of their viewers until the end of their content.

The fourth statement has a mean of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 0.782. The respondents agreed that the social media influencers they follow are credible by providing references to the content they are making and reviewing. This showed that Generation Z follows social media influencers who are experts in what they are reviewing and in what they talk about in their video content.

1.2. Attractiveness

Table 3 revealed the respondents' perception regarding the social media influencers they follow in terms of attractiveness.

Table 3
Credibility of Social Media Influencers: Attractiveness

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are charismatic.	4.24	0.699	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are good-looking.	4.19	0.748	Agree
The social media influencers I follow is/are beautiful/handsome.	4.16	0.747	Agree
The lifestyle of social media influencer(s) I follow is /are attractive.	4.24	0.735	Agree
Composite Mean	4.21		Agree

As reflected in the table, the respondents agreed with all the statements regarding attractiveness. This indicated that they follow social media influencers who are charismatic, good-looking, beautiful/handsome, and attractive. It was suggested that Generation Z is very particular

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when it comes to the social media influencers' qualities and characteristics. The standard deviation ranged from 0.699 to 0.748, indicating a low variability, which meant that the respondents shared a similar perspective regarding social media influencers' attractiveness.

Two statements, which were charismatic and attractive lifestyle, had a similar score of 4.24, indicating that the respondents follow social media influencers who had a good sense of humor and lifestyle, which were prioritized more than the physical traits. According to Kwiatek et al. (2021), for consumers to trust the recommendations of social media influencers, they should have significant expertise in a specific area, have charisma, and maintain respect from the viewers. Their credibility affects the general perception of viewers regarding their content and might also affect the recommendations they put forth in the online world.

The lowest mean was 4.16, which suggested that social media influencers being beautiful/handsome can still result in more followers, but not as much compared to charisma, good looks, and an attractive lifestyle.

1.3. Trustworthiness

Table 4 detailed the respondents' perspective regarding the social media influencers' trustworthiness.

Table 4
Credibility of Social Media Influencers: Trustworthiness

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are dependable.	3.85	0.767	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are honest.	3.65	0.81	Agree
The social media influencer(s) I follow is/are reliable.	3.83	0.765	Agree
The lifestyle of social media influencer(s) I follow is /are sincere.	3.81	0.791	Agree
Composite Mean	3.79		Agree

The table revealed that most respondents gave similar ratings regarding trustworthiness as reflected in the minimal variation of standard deviation, ranging from 0.765 to 0.81. Generation Z agreed with all the statements of trustworthiness of the social media influencers, with a composite mean of 3.79. This result supported the study of Wiedmann & von Mettenheim (2021), which showed that among the three factors of the credibility of social media influencers, trustworthiness is the most important in an entry-level luxury fashion brand.

Among the trustworthiness characteristics, being dependable got the highest mean of 3.85. This suggested that Generation Z tends to buy on impulse if they perceive the social media influencers as dependable. A study by Koay et al. (2021) found that attractiveness and trustworthiness are the key factors driving online impulse buying. The research specifically showed that the perceived attractiveness and trustworthiness of Instagram influencers act as the primary links between their social media marketing efforts and their followers' impulsive purchases. This study provided new insights into the mechanism through which influencers' social media marketing activities affect online impulse buying through the credibility of social media influencers.

Social media influencers' reliability may also affect the impulse buying behavior of the respondents, with a mean score of 3.83, which was closest to the dependable factor. Being sincere,

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with a mean of 3.81, followed this statement. The lowest mean score was 3.65, which indicated the honesty of the social media influencers. This suggested that the respondents considered the honesty, dependability, reliability, and sincerity of the social media influencers that they chose to watch and follow.

Table 5
Summary of Mean Scores of Credibility of Social Media Influencers

Credibility of Social Media Influencers	Mean	Verbal Description
Expertise	4.05	Agree
Attractiveness	4.21	Agree
Trustworthiness	3.79	Agree
Overall Mean	4.02	Agree

Table 5 presented the summary of the three sub-variables that were used to evaluate the credibility of social media influencers: Expertise, Attractiveness, and Trustworthiness. A composite mean was computed for each category to determine the overall perception of the respondents, and each sub-variable was assessed using multiple indicators.

Attractiveness had the highest composite mean (4.21) among the three sub-variables. This indicated that the respondents strongly agree that the influencers they follow have charismatic, visually appealing traits, an attractive appearance, and an equally attractive lifestyle. Expertise followed (4.05), suggesting that respondents agreed that influencers demonstrate knowledge, provide informed opinions, and exhibit expertise in their respective fields. Trustworthiness received the lowest composite mean of 3.79, which was still rated positively, implying a relatively more moderate agreement on social media qualities such as honesty, sincerity, dependability, and reliability.

The result from the credibility of social media influencers supported the study of Sari et al. (2021), revealing that the popularity of an endorser who endorses a Korean skincare brand can significantly and positively influence the decision of consumers. Expertise, attractiveness, and trustworthiness were significant factors that may lead to an impulse buying behavior, with the aid of the popularity of an endorser.

The overall findings stated that respondents generally perceive influencers as credible across all sub-variables of the credibility of social media influencers. Visual appeal and professional knowledge appeared to have a stronger role in shaping the credibility of social media influencers compared to their personal integrity or trustworthiness.

2. Impulse Buying Behavior

Impulse buying behavior can be a result of internal or external influence, which consumers, especially Generation Z, are sometimes unaware of. This behavior is defined as a spontaneous feeling or emotion that transpires when a person is exposed to a variety of information about a product or service, which leads to an immediate purchase. This study described the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z in terms of pure, reminder, suggested, and planned impulse buying behavior.

2.1. Pure Impulse Buying Behavior

Table 6 detailed the respondents' responses regarding their online purchasing behavior in terms of pure impulse buying behavior. This occurs when a consumer engages in an unplanned purchase, considered to be the most spontaneous type of impulse buying behavior.

Table 6
Pure Impulse Buying Behavior

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
After watching videos endorsed by Social Media Influencers:			
I feel joyful to buy things suddenly and unplanned.	3.80	0.987	Agree
It makes me feel I could buy expensive things without planning beforehand.	3.21	1.222	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I make quick purchases without much thought.	3.13	1.241	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I purchase products and services that lift my mood.	3.88	0.996	Agree
I usually buy things on the spot.	3.29	1.183	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I usually buy things even if I do not need them.	3.22	1.282	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
Composite Mean	3.42		Neither Agree Nor Disagree

Table 6 showed the composite mean of 3.42, which described the respondents' pure impulse buying behavior as may or may not be affected after being exposed to social media influencers' endorsements. The study of Badgaiyan and Verma (2014) supported the result of this study since they found that not all consumers are strongly into impulsive buying behavior. Some of the respondents remain indecisive due to limited budget, lack of emotional involvement, and lack of contextual information. The result suggested that some respondents' internal conflict between desire and control leads to neutral responses in impulse buying behavior.

Generation Z's agreed that they feel joyful in buying things that are unplanned and, on impulse, have a weighted mean of 3.80. In addition, they also agreed to purchase products that lift their moods, which had a weighted mean of 3.88. This revealed that there was a positive emotional effect among respondents if they were able to purchase a product or service without having much thought. On the other hand, the other four statements having a result of "Neither Agree Nor Disagree" were critical factors since respondents might still make pure impulse buying behavior on products such as accessories, shoes, and apparel being endorsed by the social media influencers.

The standard deviation, ranging from 0.987 to 1.282, indicated a moderate variability of the responses. It suggested that the respondents' perception was more diverse, and they did not fully agree or disagree on the statements relating to pure impulse buying behavior.

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2.2. Reminder Impulse Buying Behavior

Table 7 revealed the respondents' responses regarding their online purchasing behavior in terms of reminder impulse buying behavior.

Table 7
Reminder Impulse Buying Behavior

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
After watching videos endorsed by Social Media Influencers:			
I buy products or avail services even if I do not plan to purchase them at first.	3.26	1.207	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I can buy products or avail services because I recall an earlier experience about them.	3.70	0.931	Agree
I buy products or avail services when the home stock has run out.	3.96	0.889	Agree
I buy products or avail services because it evokes a previous need.	3.82	0.868	Agree
I think about where to use the products as I see or watch it.	4.08	0.8	Agree
I buy products because it reminds me that I actually need it.	4.07	0.825	Agree
Composite Mean	3.82		Agree

Table 7 showed that the standard deviation ranged from 0.8 to 1.207. Most of the statements were of low variability, indicating that responses were generally consistent among the respondents. For the first statement, buying products or availing of services without prior planning reflected a moderate variability, suggesting a more diverse perception among the respondents. The composite mean was 3.82, which suggested that overall, the respondents "Agree" on their reminder impulse buying behavior.

Based on the result, Generation Z has the tendency to act on impulse buying behavior when they recall or see an item that reminds them of their supplies running low. The study of Cho et al. (2025) mentioned the same result as this study. They explored how nostalgia impacts impulse buying tendencies, with variations by gender. It has been found that memory-related triggers can lead to unplanned purchases upon consumers recalling prior experiences or having insufficient stock, conceptually aligning with reminder impulse buying behavior.

Thinking about the actual use of the product upon seeing or watching it has the highest mean score of 4.08, which indicates that the respondents consider the products they see or watch and may have the tendency to buy if they find it useful. Whereas, buying products or availing services without prior planning has the lowest weighted mean of 3.26, showing that the respondents may agree or may not agree to purchase a product or service without prior planning. This indicated that they may still make purchases depending on the product and other factors that may entice them to buy.

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2.3. Suggested Impulse Buying Behavior

Table 8 specified the respondents' responses regarding their online purchasing behavior in terms of suggested impulse buying behavior.

Table 8
Suggested Impulse Buying Behavior

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
After watching videos endorsed by Social Media Influencers:			
I buy products or avail services even though I just saw it for the first time.	3.13	1.15	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I buy products or avail services I never thought about at all.	2.96	1.2	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
My unconscious needs surface when I see an appropriate product.	3.45	1.05	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
Content creators make me buy a product.	3.57	1.03	Agree
I buy things because it makes me feel "this has to be mine."	3.41	1.17	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
It suddenly makes me feel I need to buy the product.	3.53	1.11	Agree
Composite Mean	3.34		Neither Agree Nor Disagree

The table revealed that when it comes to purchasing a product, respondents may or may not engage in suggested impulse buying, depending on the visualized/ perceived need as they see the product for the first time. This has been supported by the composite mean of 3.34, resulting in "Neither Agree Nor Disagree" response from the respondents. This suggested that social media influencers' techniques in advertising a product may still lead to impulse buying among Generation Zs, especially if they focus on the benefits of the product. The result of the study conducted by Sangalang et al. (2017) shared similar results with this study. Shopping enjoyment and promotional approach have been found to significantly influence impulse buying tendencies. In contrast, in-store ambiance, in-store browsing, and the presence of salespersons do not have a significant influence on the impulse buying behavior.

The standard deviation, ranging from 1.03 to 1.20, indicated a moderate variability in the responses of Generation Z. This suggested that while there was a general agreement among the respondents, there were also noticeable differences in the strength of their perspective. This may reflect the varying personal experiences or exposure to social media influencers. Among the six statements, only two items obtained an "Agree", which pertained to buying a product because of the content creators and the feeling of 'need' to buy the product.

The highest weighted mean was 3.57, which stated that content creators can make them buy a product. This further suggested that the respondents' exposure to social media influencers can have a strong impact on impulse buying behavior. The lowest mean was 2.96, which indicates that the respondents may or may not buy products or avail services that they never thought about at all. This suggested that there was still a possibility of impulse buying, depending on whether they would be enticed by the social media influencer.

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2.4. Planned Impulse Buying Behavior

Table 9 specified the respondents' responses regarding their online purchasing behavior in terms of planned impulse buying behavior. This type of impulse buying behavior exists when there is an availability of discounts, special deals, and vouchers that come with a product.

Table 9
Planned Impulse Buying Behavior

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
After watching videos endorsed by Social Media Influencers:			
I buy products or avail services because I want to take advantage of the promotion.	3.74	1.001	Agree
I visit the shopping site with a shopping list to avail the great deal offered on the products and services.	3.81	0.927	Agree
I buy products or avail services when the offered deals are very attractive.	3.98	0.825	Agree
I immediately buy a product/service because it makes me believe it is useful.	3.60	1.023	Agree
I buy things to keep in the closet or stock to be used in the future.	3.46	1.111	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
I buy products because I need them.	4.34	0.737	Agree
Composite Mean	3.82		Agree

The table explained that Generation Z can be enticed to purchase a product or service if there are promotions, coupons, discounts, special deals, and other similar offers given with the presence of social media influencers. This was shown on the composite mean of 3.82, in which the respondents answered "Agree" in general. The standard deviation showed a low to moderate range (0.737 to 1.111), suggesting a relatively consistent agreement with most of the statements. The findings of Sangalang et al. (2017) supported the results of this study and revealed that the consumers or shoppers in the fifth district of Cavite were considered as planned impulse buyers. Although in this study, the respondents were young professionals and college students, the study of Sangalang et al. (2017) focused on respondents in which the majority of shoppers are female, belonging to the age bracket of 42-49, and mostly married.

The respondents agreed to the indicator that they buy products because they needed them, reflecting a weighted mean of 4.34, which was considered the highest mean among the other indicators. This signified that the respondents purchased products out of necessity. On the other hand, the respondents may or may not engage in buying things to keep them in the closet or store them for future use. This indicator had the lowest mean score of 3.46 and had the greatest variability, with a standard deviation of 1.111. It received a "Neither Agree Nor Disagree" response on average, compared to the other indicators. This suggested that Generation Z may still be enticed to make a planned impulse buying behavior depending on the social media influencers, whose content emphasized usefulness and variety of promotions to the product or service being advertised.

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Table 10
Summary of Mean Scores of Impulse Buying Behavior

Impulse Buying Behavior	Mean	Verbal Description
Pure	3.42	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
Reminder	3.82	Agree
Suggested	3.34	Neither Agree Nor Disagree
Planned	3.82	Agree
Overall Mean	3.6	Agree

Table 10 presented the summary of the four sub-variables that were used to evaluate the impulse buying behavior in the study, namely: Pure, Reminder, Suggested, and Planned. A composite mean was computed for each category to determine the overall perception of the respondents regarding their tendency to buy in an impulse after watching videos endorsed by social media influencers. Each sub-variable was assessed using multiple indicators.

Planned impulse buying behavior and reminder impulse buying behavior both had a composite mean of 3.82, corresponding to a verbal description of "Agree". This suggested that respondents were influenced by promotions, great deals, and perceived need for a product, often recalling previous needs or an earlier experience. Respondents may visit online shopping platforms with a shopping list and may take advantage of attractive offers. This is aligned with the results of the study of Park et al. (2018), in which, by analyzing the mobile promotional data and transaction records, both price discounts and free sample coupons can increase customers' intention to purchase, as well as their spending in the redemption period. In addition, free sample coupons exhibit a lasting impact that, even when the promotion ends, leads to sustained, gradual purchases.

Pure impulse buying behavior and suggested impulse buying behavior received lower composite means of 3.42 and 3.34, respectively. Both were under the verbal description of "Neither Agree Nor Disagree". This indicated a mixed or neutral sentiment among the respondents for these behaviors. While some statements received an "Agree" description, the overall composite score implied that these types of impulse buying were not as widespread or were less consciously driven by the respondents compared to planned and reminder impulse buying.

The results revealed that social media influencers' endorsements through their video content were more effective in triggering planned and reminder impulse buying behavior rather than purely spontaneous or suggested buying behavior.

3. Pearson's Correlation and Multiple Linear Regression between Credibility of Social Media Influencers and Impulse Buying Behavior

Table 11 demonstrated Pearson's Correlation results between the credibility of social media influencers to the overall impulse buying behavior of Generation Z respondents. Meanwhile, Table 12 and Table 13 showed the Multiple Linear Regression, determining how well the independent variables (expertise, attractiveness, trustworthiness) predicted the dependent variable (impulse buying behavior). Furthermore, this was determined to be the strongest among the factors of credibility that resulted in impulse buying behavior of Generation Z.

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Table 11

Credibility of Social Media Influencers and Impulse Buying Behavior: Correlation Matrix

		Expertise		Attractiveness		Trustworthiness	
Impulse Buying Overall	Pearson's r	0.323	Moderate Relationship	0.266	Weak Relationship	0.336	Moderate Relationship
	df	401		401		401	
	p-value	< .001	Significant	< .001	Significant	< .001	Significant

The matrix revealed that expertise had a moderate positive correlation with impulse buying behavior of Generation Z ($r=0.323$, $p < .001$). Therefore, the hypothesis was supported. This implied that as respondents perceive social media influencers to be more skilled and knowledgeable on the product or service being advertised, their likelihood of engaging in impulse buying increases.

Attractiveness, on the other hand, was found to have a weak positive correlation with impulse buying ($r=0.266$, $p < .001$). Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted. While this was still considered to be statistically significant, the strength of this relationship is lower than that of expertise and trustworthiness. This implied that even though a physical appeal of social media influencers can encourage impulse buying behavior, it may not be as enticing compared with the knowledge and reliability of social media influencers that the respondents follow.

Lastly, trustworthiness of social media influencers showed the highest correlation among the three credibility variables, having a moderate positive correlation ($r=0.336$, $p < .001$) with impulse buying behavior. Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted. This indicated that Generation Zs were more likely to engage in impulse buying behavior once they viewed social media influencers as honest, reliable, credible, and dependable.

All correlations were statistically significant at $p < .001$, indicating that the likelihood of these findings occurring by chance was very low. The results suggested that while all the credibility of social media influencers positively correlates to impulse buying behavior, trustworthiness and expertise have a stronger impact compared to attractiveness. The result was found to be aligned with the previous research from Liu and Zheng (2024) entitled "The Persuasive Power of Social Media Influencers in Brand Credibility and Purchase Intention". According to the findings of their study, the informative nature of social media influencers' contents, along with their authenticity and likeness, positively influence the development of emotional connection with the influencer. This kind of one-sided connection enhanced followers' intention to purchase and their perception of the brand's credibility.

Table 12
Model Fit Measures

Model	R ²
1	0.145

Table 12 indicated that the coefficient of determination for Model 1 is 0.145. This suggested that the impulse buying behavior has approximately 14.5% of the variance which can be explained by the predictors in the model. The model demonstrated some explanatory power; however, there is a relatively low R² value, implying that 85.5% which is a substantial proportion of the variance, was attributed to other factors that were not captured by the model.

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Table 13
Credibility of Social Media Influencers and Impulse Buying Behavior: Multiple Linear Regression

Model Coefficients - Impulse Buying Overall					
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p	Interpretation
Expertise	0.148	0.0694	2.13	0.034	Significant
Attractiveness	0.141	0.0563	2.49	0.013	Significant
Trustworthiness	0.198	0.0618	3.2	0.001	Significant

Table 13 showed that all three factors were found to be statistically significant predictors ($p < 0.05$): expertise (estimate = 0.148, $p = 0.034$), attractiveness (estimate = 0.141, $p = 0.013$), and trustworthiness (estimate = 0.198, $p = 0.001$). Among them, trustworthiness appeared to be the strongest predictor, having the highest coefficient. This may imply that Generation Z places a high priority on the authenticity and honesty of social media influencers when making impulse buying behavior. It also suggested that while attractiveness plays a role, Generation Z is more particular with social media influencers whom they view as experts and are also reliable and credible.

Conclusions

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were deduced:

1. Generation Z follows social media influencers who are knowledgeable, charismatic, have an attractive lifestyle, and are dependable.
2. Generation Z tends to purchase on impulse if there is a need for a certain product, especially if the purchase comes together with discounts and good promotional deals.
3. All variables under the Credibility of Social Media Influencers and Impulse Buying Behavior provided a statistical significance, indicating that there was a relationship between credibility and impulse buying tendencies among the Generation Z consumers in Angeles City, Pampanga.
4. Although all credibility factors were found to be significant, trustworthiness emerged as a notable predictor of the impulse buying behavior of Generation Z consumers.

Recommendations

The conclusion of the study led to the following recommendations:

1. Social media influencers may improve their social media presence by consistently having a good appearance, always relying on credible sources of information, and maintaining a good image to the public.
2. Social media influencers and social media marketers may trigger impulse buying tendencies by focusing their content on the benefits of the product, followed by strategic promotional deals such as discounts, even if they are for a limited time only.
3. Social media influencers will be at an advantage if they shift focus to maintaining a good image by being transparent throughout their content. They must work on building a good, long-term relationship with their followers.
4. Social media marketers need to collaborate with social media influencers who are dependable, which may be observed through the influencer's content and engagement among their followers.
5. Future researchers can build on the findings of this study by examining other variables such as influencer-consumer interaction quality, social media platform type, and the emotional state of consumers at the time of exposure to the social media influencer's content. They may also incorporate the types of impulse buying behavior to other products or services, depending on their respondents.

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